
CURRICULUM VITAE 2024

Dimitris Seferiadis

Psychologist-Psychotherapist
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Personal Information

Surname:	Seferiadis
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Education

2000-2004	Degree in Psychology Psychology Department School of Social Science Panteion University of Social and Political Sciences
1993-1997	Degree in Nursing Department of Nursing Faculty of Health and Caring Professions Technological Educational Institute (TEI) of Athens

Continuing education at the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens

- **Master's in Applied Clinical Psychology**
- **Contemporary Criminality: Theoretical Approaches, Types of Crime, and Methods of Addressing It**
- Specialized Training in Clinical Psychology-Psychosomatic Medicine
- Cognitive and Behavioral Theory and Practice
- Specializing in the Education of Children and Adolescents
- Training in Divorce Management- Parents' Divorce
- Special Education: Interdisciplinary

- Convergence Practices
- Psychotherapy: Theory and Practice
- Infant and Preschool Child Psychology

Professional Experience

European Certificate in Psychology

- Clinical Psychology
- Educational Psychology

Date:	Institution	Occupation:	Details:
2006-2008	Institute of Mental Health for Children and Adults	Director	General management, administration and representative duties
2008	Psychology and Psychotherapy Center	Supervisor of Primary Education Teachers' groups	Subjects: Childrens' mental health, management of difficult situations, parents' cooperation Psychotherapies in cases with: Psychosis, Depression, Phychosomatic problems, Organic Problems (<i>accidents, disabilities, strokes, heart disease, postoperative support</i>)
2006-2008	Society of Mental Health for Adults and Children	Establishment, Organization and Administration of Day Center, Boarding Houses and Protected Appartments	
2006-2007	Society of Social Psychiatry and Mental Health	Education Manager	

2006-2008	Society of Social Psychiatry and Mental Health	Seminars' Organization	<p>Seminars' Subjects:</p> <p>a) Psychosis and Psychotherapy 1</p> <p>b) Psychosis and Psychotherapy 2</p> <p>c) Modern Forms of Psychopathology</p> <p>Supervision of students' Practical Exercise in the context of the Masters' Program for Clinical Psychology of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens</p>
2006-2007	Society of Social Psychiatry and Mental Health	Supervisor of students in the Masters' Program for Clinical Psychology	
2006-2008	Society of Social Psychiatry and Mental Health	Scientific Director	
1994-2007	Society of Social Psychiatry and Mental Health	Scientific Director and Administrative Manager and therapist	<p>Position in the Attica Prefecture concerning "Leros II" and "Psychargos II" programs</p> <p>Under the supervision of Psychiatrist: G. Petroulakis</p>
1996-2008	Home-Based Psychiatric Treatment (HBPT)	Home Based Treatment of acute incidents	<p>Under the supervision of Psychiatrist: A. Athanasopoulos</p>
2003-2004	Center of Development and Psychotherapy	Teaching	<p>Under the supervision of Psychiatrist: R. Papatheofilou</p>
1997-1998	Day Center: "Λέσχη Φιλίας" ("Friendship Club")	Therapist	<p>Under the supervision of Psychiatrists: P. Sakellaropoulos, M.Loutsakli</p>
1995-1996	Home-Based Psychiatric Treatment (HBPT)	Therapist of acute incident patient (home based treatment)	

1995	Dromokaiteio Psychiatric Hospital	6 month Practical Exercise
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2005-Today I maintain my own Psychologist's Office at Alexandras Ave. 209
[Tel:2106462030](tel:2106462030)

Responsibilities concerning the “Society of Social Psychiatry and Mental Health”:

- **Administrative Scientific Officer**

1. Editing of Clinical Work
2. Crisis-Relapse management
3. Harmonization and coordination of therapeutic interventions
4. Organization and operation of the rehabilitation team
5. Defining of therapeutic roles
6. Evaluation of the therapeutic work
7. Problem solving within each treatment group
8. Development of actions within the community
9. Communication with the Administrative-Management level of the organization
10. Creation of rules of procedure
11. Development of Internal Education Programs

- **Clinical and Administrative supervisor of boarding houses and protected apartments**

- 2004: Director of Protected Appartments in Kastella region
- 2003-2004: Director of Kastella boarding house
- 2002: Director of Protected Appartments of Kallithea region
 Personal Therapist of boarding house's and protected appartments' members
 Head of coordination and organization of Primary Care Teams
 Educator of masters' students, psychology students, young professionals in mental health, and T.E.I (Technological Educational Institute) students.

- **Coordinator-Therapist for patients' therapy groups**

- 1996-2004: Financial Manager of the Boarding House and the Protected Appartments
 Community Action
 Responsible for the cooperation with the Red Cross

Coordinator of volunteers' groups
TO.ΔΕ. member with Mrs. A. Frangouli as coordinator

Studies, Presentations and Conference Announcements

- **Title: “Transitional Psychiatric Structures”**

Bachelor's Thesis under the supervision of Mrs. Kleri Sinodinou

- **Title: “The phenomenon of exhaustion of mental health professionals in intermediate and asylum structures”**

Presentation at the scientific Conference: “Psychiatric Reform in Greece. Evaluation and Prospects.” 24-26 June 1999, (Hotel du Lac, Ioannina, Greece)

- **Title: “Concerns in patient choice for the «ΑΠΓΩ» boarding house.**

Presentation at the scientific Conference: “Psychiatric Reform in Greece. Evaluation and Prospects.” 24-26 June 1999, (Hotel du Lac, Ioannina, Greece)

- **Title: “Dynamic evolution of a transitional structure”**

Written Announcement at the 18th Panhellenic Congress of Psychiatry

- **Title: “Cooperation with other agencies of Piraeus region and the future contribution of the Institute of Mental Health for Children and Adults ”**

Presentation at the information day “Mental Health: A community center for mental health in Piraeus”, 17 January 2007, University of Piraeus

Publications in Press

Subjects:

- Psychism and Psychotherapy
- Problems in Psychiatric Reformation
- Stress in present times
- Postpartum psychosis
- Depression and depressing feeling
- Self destructive behavior of children and adolescents
- Women abuse
- Paedophilia and child abuse
- Homosexuality
- A new mental health community center
- Group Psychology
- Abuse of minors
- Panic attack and agoraphobia

Seminars and Conferences

Date	2005
Type	Two-Day Forum
Subject	Anatomy of learning difficulties
Institution	Multifunctional Center of Kallithea
Dates	25/02/05 - 27/05/05
Type	Seminar
Subject	Depression: Psychoanalytic Approach and Clinical Practice
Institution	Hellenic Society of psychoanalytic psychotherapy
Dates	February 2005
Type	Seminar
Institution	Masters Program in Social Psychiatry- Paedopsychiatry
Date	October 2004
Type	Seminar
Subject	Management of Psychosocial Rehabilitation Units
Rapporteur	Dr. BobGrove
Date	14-18/05/2004
Type	18 th Panhellenic Congress of Psychiatry
Date	September 2003
Type	Transnational One-day forum
Subject	The Burnout Syndrome in Psychiatry: Therapeutic and Rehabilitation Activities
Institution	K.E.K. EOMMEX
Date	11-15/11/02
Type	Deinstitutionalisation Training Program in Northumberland NHS, UK
Date	December 2001
Type	One-day forum
Subject	Depression in childhood, Depression in adults, Home based psychiatric treatment
Institution	Society of social psychiatry and mental health in cooperation with OKANA, Tauros Municipality

Date	May 2001
Type	2nd Hellenic Conference of Paedopsychiatric Society of Greece, Caravel Hotel
Subject	Psychosomatic disorders in children and adolescents: Theoretical and Clinical Approach
Dates	June 1999
Type	Scientific Conference , Hotel du Lac, Ioannina
Subjects	Psychiatric Reform in Greece. Evaluation and Prospects.
Dates	1995-1996
Type	Two-Year Psychoanalytical Seminar
Institution	Kallithea mental health Institute
Scientific Supervisor	Mr. P. Sakellaropoulos
Dates	24-28/01/1996
Type	2 nd Seminar of the masters program in social psychiatry, Athens
Dates	26-29/01/1995
Type	1 st Seminar of the masters program in social psychiatry of children and adults, Athens

Other Activities	
	Member at the Institute of History of Psychoanalysis and Modern Clinical Practices
	Member of the administrative board at the Institute of Mental Health for Children and Adults
	Member at the Association of Greek Psychologists, registration number: 1393
	9year Personal Psychoanalytic Psychotherapy
Therapist	Mr. V. Falaras, psychiatrist, psychoanalyst, trainer at the Hellenic Society of Psychoanalytic Psychotherapy

	Supervisions in the context of psychotherapeutic work of Home-Based Psychiatric Treatment groups in a weekly or monthly basis
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Dates	2003 - 2007
Type	Psychoanalysis Texts Analysis
Instructor	Mr. A. Vasilias, member of the Hellenic Society of Psychoanalytic Psychotherapy
Dates	2004 - 2011
	Personal Supervision (once per week)
Supervisor	Mr. G. Maniadakis psychiatrist, member at the Hellenic Society of Psychoanalytic Psychotherapy